

Development of web-based accounts receivable management system for St. Dominic Medical Center Accounting Office

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Abstract

Hospitals are experiencing difficulty at keeping tracks of patient's data and monitoring the accounts receivable, payable records and billing transactions under HMO or Health Maintenance Organization due to numerous numbers of patients to be encoded. The importance of keeping track of records is to monitor all the data that are recorded in the database. The users need a way to store and analyze data such as patients' information, Accounts payable and billing transactions into a comprehensible report that would otherwise be a long and tedious task. The proponents developed a web-based Accounts Receivable Management System for St. Dominic Medical Center Accounting Office that will help ease the process of recording and monitoring of patient's accounts receivable, payable records and billing transactions. The system also relies on encoding the patient's information and record transactions. The agile method was used to improve the analysis, research design and development of the proposed system. The Acceptability of the system is based on the system performance and system requirements hence the outcome has enhanced the process of how the user record, store and monitor the patient's accounts receivable and billing transactions in the designated workplace. The system maintenance is an on-going activity and administrator will have to check and update design errors, documentations and update the user support. The research has been evaluated by nine (9) end users and two (2) expert users, obtaining a total output for the level of satisfaction which is a 3.54 that is considered as "acceptable".

Keywords: *Queuing system, queuing theory, Agile Methodology.*

Introduction

A Health Maintenance Organization (HMO) is a system or association that gives medical coverage inclusion to a monthly or yearly charge. HMO is comprised of a gathering of restorative protection suppliers that limit inclusion to therapeutic guide gave from specialists that are under the agreement of the HMO. These agreements take into account premiums to be lower since the wellbeing patients coordinated to them, yet these agreements likewise add extra confinements to the HMO's individuals.

HMO subscribers pay a month to month or yearly premium to get to medicinal administrations in the association's system of suppliers but at the same time are constrained to accepting human services from these contracted restorative suppliers. A guaranteed individual must get his consideration and administrations from specialists under the HMO organize, be that as it may, some out-of-arrange therapeutic consideration can be secured under the HMO. These sorts of administrations incorporate crisis care and dialysis.

Accounts Receivable Management System for St. Dominic Medical Center caters HMO records of bills, through the web-based system, a monitoring and notification feature for HMOs can be catered. It is a web-based application that helps the administrators of the accounting office of St. Dominic Medical Center to keep and organize the records being kept by the systems database and to present processed information in a meaningful way.

The traditional method of keeping accounts receivable records are through manual logging using papers and journals. This can be a tedious task and time consuming for the administrator and can be costly for the resources being used compared to Accounts Receivable Management System. In comparison to the traditional methods; it is much more cost effective, less time consuming and can be done effortlessly.

The processed information was displayed in real time. Which would otherwise be difficult to tally by hand because it is computed from huge data sets? It is precise and takes just a second to be calculated. The system can transform raw data into useful information which can be used in the future for reference.

The accountants are provided with the account receivable modules of the ARMS, which will result to efficient and effective records of monitoring HMO and patients accounts payable. The insurance companies are provided a record of bills due and paid. With the modules provided, an operation ease can be caused by the Accounts Receivable Management System for St. Dominic Medical Center.

Because there are lots of money and parties involved, sales and purchases of items on credit done by travel bureau firms require careful handling. The goal of this study is to develop information systems to manage account payables and receivables connected to the purchase and selling of credit-based tour packages (Karma & Susanti, 2018).

The cash conversion cycle (CCC) is a dynamic measure of liquidity. Days in accounts receivable (A/R), days in accounts payable (A/P), and days in inventory make up the cash conversion cycle. Richard and Laughlin's (1980) method illustrates the key contrast between the cash conversion cycle and conventional measurements of liquidity; whereby, CCC is used to assess liquidity from the standpoint of a company's ability to continue operating. The current ratio and quick ratio (current assets and current liabilities) are generated mostly from the balance sheet, but the cash conversion cycle (days in A/R, days in A/P, and days inventory) is produced primarily from the income statement and are measured over a specific duration of time (Upadhyay & Smith, 2018 as cited in Gapenski & Reiter, 2016).

The above ratio must be considered in two ways: a) as a percentage of values and b) the date of expiration of the items reflected in the ratio, because the same value is worth more if the date of expiration of receivables is shorter than the date of expiration of liabilities, which must be met using cash generated from receivables collection (Curtis & Roupas, 2009).

The average number of days it takes a hospital to obtain payment from a payer (e.g., insurance company, patient, government) after delivering health care services to a patient is measured by Days Patients Accounts Receivable. A high number of days patients accounts receivable indicates a low level of efficiency since the hospital is giving services on credit to clients who are waiting longer to pay (Dong, 2015). The average duration for which sales revenue is kept in accounts receivable is measured by the receivable turnover ratio. This ratio is frequently used to represent the efficacy and efficiency of receivables collection (Denčić-Mihajlov, 2013).

The scope and limitations of Accounts Receivable Management System for St. Dominic Medical Center are for the following users:

- Management Information System (MIS) Administrators
- Billing Officers (Administrator)
- Health Maintenance Organizations
- Patients

Modules are created for the stated user levels, that will focus more on tracking and monitoring the accounts receivable of St. Dominic Medical Center.

Methodology

Figure 1 Agile Model

Figure 1 shows the Agile Model used by the proponents to develop the Accounts Receivable Management System.

The proponents use this step-by-step method to develop the functions of the system. The proponents gathered information from the client to include in the requirements needed in developing the system. The features of the system are easy to access and user-friendly for the client. The implementation of the system will help the proponents to test the functionalities of the system for errors and bugs.

This will also allow the proponents to distinguish if the project will need some modifications and if the deployment of the system would be able to adapt in the environment. If the proponents found any errors in the system, they must start from method 1 which is planning and so on with the testing phase. If the application does not have any errors or bugs, maintenance will be implemented after the deployment.

Figure 2 Conceptual framework

Figure 2 shows the conceptual framework of the Accounts Receivable Management System.

Figure 3 Context Flow Diagram

Figure 3 shows the Context Flow Diagram of the Accounts Receivable Management System.

Level of Satisfaction

To test the project, the researchers observed the functionality, reliability, usability, efficiency, maintainability, and portability of the system.

Functionality refers to the system's capabilities when performing under its purpose.

Reliability refers to the system's maintainability, stability, and flexibility.

Usability refers to the system's graphical user interface.

Efficiency refers to the system's performance.

Maintainability refers to the system's availability under enhancement.

Portability refers to the capability of the system to be used in different environment.

The proponents used the guidance of the table below to evaluate the level of satisfaction for the developed project.

Table 1 Level of satisfaction of the project

Scale	Range	Interpretation
5	4.51-5.00	Highly Acceptable
4	3.51-4.50	Moderately Acceptable
3	2.51-3.50	Acceptable
2	1.51-2.50	Needs Improvement
1	1.00-1.50	Not Acceptable

Results and Discussion

Respondents' Distribution

The respondents are the accounting office staffs of St. Dominic Medical Center. The system was evaluated by nine (9) front-end users and two (2) Expert users, a total of 11 respondents.

Table 2 Respondents' distribution of the project

Respondents	Frequency	Percentage
End-User	9	81.82%
Expert-User	2	18.18%
Total	11	100%

Overall Level of Satisfaction

The table below shows the overall response of the expert user and end user using the levels of satisfaction and respondent's frequency.

Table 3 Overall level of satisfaction based on respondents' distribution of the project

Category	Expert-User	End-User	Overall level of satisfaction	Rating
Functionality	2.70	4.12	3.41	Acceptable
Reliability	2.90	4.04	3.47	Acceptable
Usability	2.86	4.13	3.50	Acceptable
Efficiency	3.03	4.18	3.61	Moderately Acceptable
Maintainability	3.00	4.02	3.51	Moderately Acceptable
Portability	3.10	3.90	3.50	Acceptable
AVERAGE	2.93	4.07	3.50	Acceptable

Based on the table, the system functionality secures “acceptable” with an average of 3.41. The total average for the end-user is 4.12 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 2.70 which is “acceptable”.

The reliability of the system secures “acceptable” with an average of 3.47. The total average for the end-user is 4.04 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 2.90 which is “acceptable”.

The system usability secures “acceptable” with an average of 3.50. The total average for the end-user is 4.13 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 2.86 which is “acceptable”.

The system efficiency secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.61. The total average for the end-user is 4.18 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 3.03 which is “acceptable”.

The system maintainability secures “moderately acceptable” with an average of 3.51. The total average for the end-user is 4.02 which is “moderately acceptable”. The total average for the expert user is 3.00 which is “acceptable”.

The system portability secures “acceptable” with an average of 3.50. The total average for the end-user is 3.90 which is “acceptable”. The total average for the expert-user is 3.10 which is “acceptable”.

Results show that the overall level satisfaction is 3.50 that is considered as “Acceptable”. It is revealed that the system is working and operational. Effective accounts receivable management is critical and strategic since it impacts a company's financial performance and value. The ability of a company to synchronize cash inflows and outflows while developing a cash flow management plan is critical to its financial performance. Accounts receivable management aims to increase shareholder wealth. Receivables are substantial investments in company assets that are assessed in terms of their net present value, similar to capital budgeting projects (Mbula et al., 2016 as cited in Emery et al., 2004).

Conclusions

Based on the results, the overall level satisfaction is “acceptable” for the users, mainly accounting staffs of St. Dominic Medical Center. It shows that system is working and operational. The Accounts Receivable Management System for St. Dominic Medical Center only relies on the records of the patients, with HMO, and not on the patients conducted transactions that are not through an insurance company. In this manner, the system is only limited of patients with HMOs due to the functionality requirements of the client.

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